

Bahar Noorizadeh's Weird Economies

On Post-Media Speculative Politics

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the role of speculation as a tactical strategy in the context of post-media activism, with a specific focus on the work of artist Bahar Noorizadeh and her piece "Teslaim: Economics at the end of the end of the future." In an era marked by exponential technological advancement and the omnipresence of media, traditional forms of activism and artistic expression are being redefined. Post-media activism represents a paradigm shift, incorporating new media, digital platforms, and speculative narratives to engage with socio-political issues.

The concept of speculation is situated within the broader discourse of tactical media, which emphasizes the subversive and interventionist potential of media practices. This theoretical framework serves as a lens through which to analyze Noorizadeh's artistic practice and her engagement with speculative strategies. Central to the analysis is an exploration of how "Teslaim" encapsulates the ethos of post-media activism through its use of speculative economy (see "Weird Economy") and technological imaginaries. Her work, offers a nuanced critique of techno-capitalism and its reverberations across society. By employing speculative fiction and visual storytelling, "Teslaim" not only envisions alternative futures but also exposes the power dynamics inherent in contemporary technological discourses. "...The alternative cannot be speculation only as a tool to reach more efficiency either or manage more information or solve problems. According to Bahar the contradictory notion of speculative imagination could be used instead to embrace risk and communalize the black box of economic models and their history. The aim to ask ourselves what a redistributive historical justice look like for the present."(Synthetic Minds Podcast #02: Technocapital Singularities | Medialab-Matadero Madrid, n.d.) Furthermore, the paper delves into the ways in which Noorizadeh's artistic practice blurs the boundaries between aesthetic experimentation and political intervention. Through a multidisciplinary approach that combines film, videogames, and digital media, "Teslaim" exemplifies the capacity of post-media activism to co-opt and transmute dominant narratives to provoke critical reflection. The paper also considers the reception and circulation of "Teslaim" within the art world and digital spheres, highlighting how

speculative interventions can resonate beyond traditional exhibition spaces. By embracing speculation as a mode of resistance and world-making, Noorizadeh's work exemplifies the transformative power of art in an age of media ubiquity and digital acceleration. Ultimately, for Bahar rather than fighting speculation, which from her perspective became a primary mode of addressing issues from the left, we need to be able to think about how to socialize speculation, communalize speculation, how to risk together, better.

KEYWORDS

Capitalism; Speculative Theory; Post-Media; Tactical Media

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The alternative of no alternative

"There is no alternative" is the phrase that recalls Margaret Thatcher's famous speech enshrining the cultural and political hegemony of the neoliberal model. The universal capitalist free market model that marked, according to Francis Fukuyama in *The End of History and the last Man* in 1992, the inadvertent conclusion of any project of human society.(Fukuyama, 1992) Thirty years later it is still difficult to imagine an alternative course of history, but at the same time we find ourselves at the impasse of not being able to imagine how this model can continue unchallenged. In the face of the fractures and crises that characterize our contemporary times, such as ecological collapse, migration crisis, pandemics and wars that are accelerating on a global scale, the neoliberal system is mutating into an increasingly dysfunctional model of authoritarian necropolitics.(Mbembe & Corcoran, 2019)

Mark Fisher's 2009 book, *Capitalist Realism: Is There No Alternative?* focuses on the argument that art and imagination have been monopolized by capitalism since the rise of neoliberalism.(Fisher, 2009)

Fisher uses the term "capitalist realism" to describe this ideological formation, where capitalism presents itself as the only realistic and inevitable system. Amidst ongoing discussion, a thorough examination of capitalist realism exposes inherent flaws in the ways capitalism portrays itself. The nuanced nature of capitalist realism imitation exemplifies the enduring significance of this notion for contemporary artists. Nevertheless, this particular issue's retrospective analysis of the subject demonstrates that the idea of capitalism as the most encompassing and practical system had already incited simultaneous reactions from artists worldwide even before Thatcher and Reaganomics hegemony. Fisher's assessment of contemporary art's susceptibility to capitalist co-optation resonates with the longtime criticisms of the avant-garde movement in the 1960s.(Faris, 2015)

The notion of "Capitalist Realism" was initially presented in May 1963 by a collective of West German artists: Gerhard Richter, Konrad Lueg, Sigmar Polke, and Manfred Kuttner;(Tate, n.d.) and separately by Japanese artist Akasegawa Genpei in his manifesto *Theses on "Capitalist realism"*(Akasegawa, 1964) within an interval of less than a year. Both in the German and Japanese contexts, the artists utilized the term to establish a comparison between the representational systems of communism and capitalism, drawing on the term's suggestive association with Socialist Realism. Socialist Realism, a government endorsed artistic trend that emerged in the Soviet Union during the early 1930s, commonly portrayed idealized images of collective work and exalted the working class. In contrast, the artists proposed that a capitalist realist approach could portray the capitalist equivalent: commercials featuring new consumer products and images of satisfied customers. This implicit connection was used to criticize the widespread impact of capitalist culture on modern art and society.

Parallel to the western avant-garde critique of capitalism realism, in the 1960s, a number of Soviet technologists envisioned computers as machines that could enable automated communism and cybernetics as a solution to problems that they were confronting in the centrally planned economy.

After Scarcity (2018) by Bahar Noorizadeh is an experimental film essay that investigates this history by following the cyberneticians of the Soviet Union who were working toward the goal of constructing a fully automated planned economy.(Dis — *After Scarcity*, n.d.) The movie makes the suggestion that these alternative histories of economic technology should be revisited in order to open up access to potential futures. It rushes through decades of history to demonstrate how contingent pasts make imaginative futures more tangible, and it raises questions about how we might use computation to move beyond digital feudalism and toward new utopias. To be more specific, it argues that socialism was an integral part of the communist technological evolution and that computation does not necessarily involve the financialized autocracy that exists in the current society we live in.

If the reality of our political imagination is relegated to an idea of realism interwoven with an economic system that limits its possibilities, can a viable answer to this problem be the use of art and speculative narratives that imagine alternative reality systems, unexplored economies, and hidden libidinal desires? A question then arises. How can this collective impasse be overcome?

The alternative of no alternative

Figure 1. Bahar Noorizadeh, *Teslaism: Economics at the End of the End of the Future*, film still, 2022

The artist, writer, and filmmaker Bahar Noorizadeh critically examines the relationships between speculative finance, capitalism, and the arts. Noorizadeh, who was born in Iran in 1988, explores in her work the intricate connections between speculative fiction and human history, especially as they relate to and are influenced by each other in the context of finance, urban life, and economics. Her academic formation culminated in her completion of a Doctorate in Art from Goldsmiths, University of London. Noorizadeh's contributions to the field go beyond her artistic endeavors; she also continues her practice and research as an associate lecturer at the Design Academy Eindhoven and the RCA School of Architecture.(Bahar noorizadeh, n.d.) In her work, she extensively

researches the histories of economics, cybernetic socialism, and the different activist tactics used to oppose the commodification of life and living spaces.

Noorizadeh raises important concerns about what redistributive historical justice might entail in modern society through her art.

Weird Economies, a co-authored and socially conscious project founded by Noorizadeh, aims to chart out economic imaginaries that deviate dramatically from the traditional financial structures.

By utilizing a chrono-political approach that integrates past, present, and future economic opportunities, this initiative functions as a journal, programming space, and social experimentation site. (*Weird Economies*, 2024)

In her project "*Teslaism: Economics at the end of the end of the future*" she provides a critical view of the possible outcomes of unregulated capitalism and economic expansion. Noorizadeh envisions a dystopian future influenced by the values and ideas of tech baron Elon Musk through video games and musical performances. Noorizadeh's use of sarcasm and speculative worldbuilding emphasizes the lack of social and environmental sustainability in perpetual economic growth. Her analysis investigates how the work addresses the increasing authority and impact of technology leaders on society. Through her exploration of Musk's influence, Noorizadeh raises important questions about the consequences of unchecked technological advancement and the power dynamics at play in shaping our future. By blending elements of fiction with real-world concerns, it serves as a critique of the potential pitfalls of prioritizing profit over people and planet.

"Teslaism" is a narrativized third-person racing and musical video game that showcases Elon Musk and his autonomous vehicle, which also serves as his romantic partner and mentor, on their journey to a shareholder meeting set against the backdrop of a futuristic Berlin transformed into a gamified landscape. The narrative leverages the newly established Gigafactory in Berlin to explore the concept of "Teslaism," a term coined to describe the evolution from Post-Fordism to a new era characterized by enhanced production and consumption mechanisms. (Noorizadeh, 2023) This era is distinguished by its reliance on sophisticated narrative techniques, financial storytelling, and the creative envisioning of future aesthetics. In the author's words: "*The idea of Teslaism emerged out of a segment of my PhD work that was trying to demarcate financialization as an era distinct from what's commonly known as neoliberalism with its post-fordist mode of production. The transformations in the automobile industry have historically provided that storytelling device to read ideological shifts in societies and their modes of production in parallel, and the car becomes somewhat of a narrator of this history. We don't need to think too far to notice there's something different about Tesla to Toyota, which provided a prototypical image for the post-fordist paradigm. In line with political philosophers like Michel Feher, I think sharpening this distinction between what neoliberalism purported to be and what its real-world manifestation as*

financialization is, is quite important. Feher suggests that in theory, original neoliberal figureheads were trying to summon the profit-seeking entrepreneurial subject, but in the path to the formation of this subjectivity they accidentally gave birth to the credit-seeking portfolio manager. The difference is that the latter plays in the arena of speculation, whereas the former is driven by rational incentives that lead to present gains." ("Rating and Revolutions Speculative politics at the Age of Teslaism," 2023)

The game was specifically developed for the Tresor 31: Techno, Berlin, and the Great Freedom event. The game's soundtrack perfectly captures the atmosphere of the event and immerses players in a world of pulsating techno beats and futuristic visuals. The soundtrack for "Teslaism" features contributions from notable artists, including "Conic Sections" by XOR Gate, "Humanoid Fruit" by Helena Hauff, and "GRV Tr 4" by TV Victor.

Figure 2. Tresor 31st Anniversary, Kraftwerk Berlin, photo by Helge Mundt

Noorizadeh uses hyperbole to provoke thought about how the preferences and whims of people like Musk can influence the course of society in ways that might be contrary to the interests of the general public.

In addition to its direct criticism of individuals such as Musk, "Teslaism" also functions as a commentary on the contemporary power dynamics that exist between governmental entities, corporations, and individual citizens. It depicts a world where the voice and authority of democratic institutions are "one among many," while private interests dictate policies on technology, infrastructure, and more.

This not-so-hypothetical corporate takeover, which was made possible by political leaders voluntarily ceding control, brings to light more fundamental concerns regarding governance and accountability in an era characterized by the proliferation of multinational technology conglomerates. Who stands to gain from the visions of progress that are being promoted by the innovators of today's technology? What about those who might be left behind? As a result of Noorizadeh's presentation of an extreme extrapolation of current trajectories, viewers are prompted to

confront the implications of unchecked private power over public welfare.

Conclusions

Noorizadeh employs satirical imagination and an exaggerated extrapolation of current capitalist trajectories in order to emphasize the unsustainable nature of these trajectories and to warn against the accumulation of an excessive amount of power among elites who are not accountable for their actions. Criticism focuses primarily on the potential consequences that could occur in the real world as a result of unchecked growth, the influence of corporations, and the visions of elite technological leaders. Noorizadeh's political strategy propose that it is possible to push the boundaries of our current economic system and stimulate innovative thought by employing artistic expression and the dissemination of speculative narratives. Through the utilization of creativity and imagination, we are able to overcome the constraints of realism and come up with original solutions to the crisis that we are all experiencing collectively. We have the ability to inspire new perspectives and solutions that have the potential to reshape our future if we challenge traditional norms and investigate alternative possibilities. By being open to speculation, we are able to imagine a world in which economic structures are reimagined and overcome for the purpose of improving society as a whole.

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